

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

Experiments on critical thinking, autonomy and AI

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Deliverable Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence in multiple aspects of our daily lives poses a great challenge in shaping civic participation within societies. Effective civic engagement finds its foundation in the empowerment of citizens who actively participate in public discourse, and in the articulation of their viewpoints. Understanding the dynamics that underpin trust in democratic institutions in this new context is thus important.

Module A questions individuals' capacity to navigate AI-based content and recommendations while safeguarding their autonomy and free will. Module B examines the requisites for the utilisation of AI to preserve institutional trust. Indeed, the use of AI in a wide range of fields could generate situations that are, or are perceived to be, unfair, thereby threatening the social balance established between members of the same community. Module C puts the new challenges posed by technological transformations into perspective, by analysing historical precedents and how they have shaped culture and social interactions over centuries.

Through a comprehensive exploration and assessment, modules A, B and C of KT4D's Social Risk Toolkit will seek to address an important challenge: identify exactly where regulation is needed to ensure that AI benefits society as a whole, and identify the conditions for trust in social institutions, in order to guarantee effective public debate and societal choices are made by citizens themselves.

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Experimentation and action research

General methodology

The experimental component of Module A aims to further characterise internet users' behaviours when faced with online choices potentially undermining their autonomy: how people evaluate AI-generated information and/or content selected through AI-based algorithms, and how people are influenced by AI-based algorithms in their online choices.

Are people more vigilant when they know how AI works and/or when they are aware of the intentions of those who provide them with this content? Here, we study the evaluation of information with manipulated sources (AI vs. Expert vs. Layperson), as well as manipulated levels of accuracy and relevance. The stakes associated with the truthfulness of information are also measured and included as a variable for assessing the propensity to exercise critical thinking. (Experiment 1)

Regarding online choices, our aim is to clarify what consent means in situations when people are asked to agree on terms and conditions, by monitoring the decisions people make in such situations and by examining the contextual factors that matter most. (Experiment 2)

Based on its action research activities, this module will contribute to the development of concrete strategies that prioritise sound ethical considerations.

Preregistration of experimental protocols

Experiment 1: Exploration of critical attitudes in response to information provided by AI vs. human sources

The aim of experiment 1 is to **observe the way in which individuals mobilise their epistemic vigilance with regard to information produced by ChatGPT**, compared with the same information provided by a human (either an expert or a non-expert). The aim is to see 1) whether people's attitudes towards the information produced by ChatGPT are similar to those towards the same information provided by an expert or a non-expert; 2) whether these attitudes depend on the stakes associated with the situation; and 3) whether knowledge of how AI works (and, more generally, digital literacy and the culture of AI) influences participants' critical attitudes.

This action research will then enable us to better direct communication efforts aimed at the general public: should we provide better information on how AI works, or should the so-called lack of critical thinking be interpreted more as a lack of motivation to discern truth from falsehood?

Rationale

Trust is an attitude whereby the individuals agree to place themselves in a vulnerable situation on the basis of positive expectations regarding the intentions or behaviour of another person or entity (Baghramian, 2020). Whereas in the case of epistemic trust between people, the main components of trust are the benevolence and competence of the source¹, in the case of trust in a technology, the

¹ For instance, a source's credibility influences the perception of the credibility of stories (Compton et al., 2021; Lewandowsky & van der Linden, 2021; Roozenbeek & van der Linden, 2019), with highly credible sources reducing the perception of implausibility in fairly implausible statements but increasing the perception of implausibility in very implausible statements.

expectation relates to the systematicity, and reliability of the help provided (Kaplan et al., 2023). It involves the belief that technology will consistently work in a functional, and predictable manner to provide useful and reliable results.

What about trust toward chatbots, such as ChatGPT? Users may experience emotional trust when interacting with chatbots, and individuals tend to evaluate AIs as more reliable when they have a human appearance, either in their shape or in their reactions: anthropomorphism would therefore be a predictor of trust (Kaplan et al., 2023). In this context, how do people rely on information provided by AI-based systems, compared to human sources? How do certain features of the interaction influence this trust?

Arguably, there should be a link between knowing how artificial intelligence systems work and being critical about it. AI literacy encompasses the ability to recognise an AI, to understand it, to recognise that it can take many forms and cover many domains, and that a general AI replicating human intelligence does not yet exist, etc. (Long & Magerko, 2020). It is thus a set of skills through which individuals can use artificial intelligence as a tool in their professional and private lives and decide when to use AI and when to rely on human expertise instead. In that respect, Dikmen & Burns (2022) found that providing users with specific domain knowledge influences individual's trust in AI and their reliance on AI-driven suggestions. Namely, participants who were given domain knowledge relied less on the AI assistant when it provided incorrect recommendations and reported lower levels of trust in the AI's suggestions.

Research question and hypotheses

The question we are asking here is **whether individuals demonstrate critical thinking when evaluating information produced by ChatGPT** (is the information received evaluated as if it came from a human expert, or rather if it came from a non-expert?) and whether this critical attitude depends on the knowledge they have about how LLMs work. We also expect that the effort engaged to assess the reliability of a piece of information will depend on the relevance of knowing the truth of the matter on a particular question. Our hypotheses are as follows:

H1: Information provided by an AI agent will be more trusted than information provided by a non-expert source, but less trusted than information provided by an expert source.

H2: There is a positive link between AI culture (habit of use and knowledge of how LLMs work) and critical attitudes toward information provided by an AI agent. The higher the participants' AI culture, the more accurate their assessment of the information provided by an AI agent.

H3: The stakes of knowing the truth of the matter on the topic at hand will influence the epistemic vigilance of participants in all conditions.

Methodology

Participants

A sample size of **336** participants was determined using G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2007). The alpha threshold was set to 0.05, with a statistical power of $1-\beta = .98$ and an effect size of 0.15 (Fig. 1). The

chosen effect size corresponds to a **small effect size** according to the criteria established by Cohen (2009).

Since we planned to run non-parametric tests, we added 15% to our desired sample (Lehmann & D’Abrera, 1998). We anticipated that about 25% of participants would not complete the experiment and answer the control questions correctly. The estimated sample size is therefore **483** participants.

Participants are recruited via crowdpanel.io, an online platform that provides a panel of participants for polls and surveys.

Figure 1 – Results of power analysis for Experiment 1

The participants are randomly assigned to the experimental conditions (Table 1). Each experimental group therefore consists of **161** participants.

Source / Experimental group	Group n°1	Group n°2	Group n°3
Source of Scenario 1	Expert	Non-Expert	IA
Source of Scenario 2	Non-Expert	IA	Expert
Source of Scenario 3	IA	Expert	Non-Expert
Source of Scenario 1	Expert	Non-Expert	IA

Table 1 – Experimental groups (within-subject design) in Experiment 1

Material

The experimental material consists of a fully online Lime Survey. The questionnaire includes socio-demographic questions, questions related to the evaluation of the test scenarios, and additional questions regarding people's attitudes to AI. Three scenarios were designed to answer our research question and test our hypotheses: a 'Newspaper' scenario, a 'Human Resources' scenario, and a 'Pharmacist' scenario. Each scenario has three versions relative to the source of the information received: Expert, Non-Expert or AI (Box 3). In all conditions, the media used to receive the information is an online messaging system. Each version of the same scenarios only differ in a single sentence, the remaining parts of the text being identical. All participants see each modality of the design (Expert, Non-Expert, AI). The scenarios also differ between them in the potential stakes associated with using accurate information.

The three conditions of the 'Newspaper' scenario (original version in French)

Expert version. Sam is a freelancer for an online newspaper. He is writing an article for a special issue on road safety. He is looking for information on the initiatives that have proved most effective in reducing road accidents. *He finds the contact details of a specialist researcher by reading an article. During an online exchange with this specialist, he is told: "A recent study showed that 30 minutes of meditation before driving reduced the risk of a road accident by 90%".*

Non-Expert version. Sam is a freelancer for an online newspaper. He has to write an article for a special issue on road safety. He is looking for information on the initiatives that have proved most effective in reducing road accidents. *He remembers a conversation he'd had a few days earlier with one of his colleagues on this subject. During an online exchange with this colleague, he is told: "A recent study showed that 30 minutes of meditation before driving reduced the risk of a road accident by 90%".*

IA version. Sam is a freelancer for an online newspaper. He has to write an article for a special issue on road safety. He is looking for information on the initiatives that have proved most effective in reducing road accidents. *He wonders whether ChatGPT might be able to give him some ideas. During an online exchange with ChatGPT, he is told: "A recent study showed that 30 minutes of meditation before driving reduced the risk of a road accident by 90%".*

Box 1 – The three conditions of the 'Newspaper' scenario in Experiment 1

Procedure

The study is conducted entirely online. Participants complete it in the following order:

1. Information leaflet and consent form

The information leaflet describes the framework of the research, the material that is about to be presented to the participants, the duration of the study, information on the use of the data collected, respect for the confidentiality of the participants, and specifies their right to withdraw from the study at any time. A reminder that participation is voluntary, and a contact address is also given to participants. Participants then either accept or refuse to continue based on the information they have been given. If the participant does not wish to continue, the questionnaire ends there.

2. Questions about the test scenarios

Participants then access the study itself. They are presented with three scenarios. After reading each text, participants answer verification questions to check that they have correctly perceived and integrated the manipulation of the text source. They are then asked to answer two questions (presented in a 5-point-Likert scale) about the content of the scenario:

- a. One on the perceived likelihood that the information provided is true: *To what extent do you consider the information provided in this text to be true (the probability that the information in this context is true)? On a scale of 1 to 7 (1 = definitely false, 7 = definitely true)*
- b. One on whether they would be in favour of this information being used in a professional context: *In your opinion, should Sam include this information in his article? On a scale of 1 to 7 (1 = do not include this information at all in your article, 7 = absolutely must include this information in your article)*

This first part takes less than 15 minutes to complete.

3. Questions about AI and socio-demographic questions

Participants then answer questions about their experience of using artificial intelligence and their knowledge of AI systems. They are asked about their frequency of use of artificial intelligences, the contexts in which they usually use them, and their knowledge of how, e.g., ChatGPT works.

Participants then answer questions about the trust they place in artificial intelligence systems. Other questions concern issues relating to data protection, the perceived usefulness of these systems, potential risks, and ethical issues relating to the use of AI.

This part finally includes demographic questions on gender, age category and educational level, and takes about 5 minutes to answer.

4. Debriefing phase

After the questionnaire has been completed, participants are given information about the aim of the experiment, the hypotheses, and the protocol itself. They are offered the opportunity to leave a comment or ask questions. The e-mail address of the researcher is provided, and participants are told that they can contact her by email if they wish to have access to the results of the research.

The data collection for this experiment has started in September 2024.

For the statistical analyses, mixed-effect models are fitted using *R* statistical software, in order to test for the different factors of interest and random effects.

Experiment 2: The importance of epistemic intentions in ascribing responsibility to internet users when agreeing to terms and conditions

Internet users frequently encounter lengthy *Terms & Conditions* when accessing online services. Many accept these agreements without fully reading or understanding them, often motivated by attractive offers—such as a low introductory price. However, the small print can contain complex clauses, such as cumbersome cancellation procedures that users may find difficult to navigate afterwards.

This situation raises important questions about accountability: To what extent are users responsible for agreements they do not read in detail, and how much responsibility lies with service providers for the clarity of their terms? Furthermore, individual intuitions regarding these issues may vary significantly, influenced by cultural perspectives on fairness and transparency.

Rationale

The aim of Experiment 2 is to explore what people think when they accept online terms and conditions, and the extent to which they feel committed (i.e. they think they will be to blame if they don't comply with what they signed). Previous research indeed shows that these policies are often ignored (Steinfeld, 2016). This raises the question of what responsibility lies with the users. If it turns out that the *Terms & Conditions* that they have signed do not suit them in the end, is it fair that they should be penalised? In other words, how committed are we when such a commitment is made under conditions where the effort required to acquaint oneself with the necessary information is unreasonably heavy?² The question of the role of intentions in interactions and exchanges between individuals and online companies is not trivial. By exploring individuals' pre-existing beliefs about the intentions, knowledge, and common ground of these entities, we can better understand how accepting cookies or terms and conditions may put users in vulnerable positions.

Research question and hypotheses

We make several hypotheses:

H1: Hypothesis on the cost of epistemic action. If too much is required to know, the user can hardly be blamed for not having bothered to find out. (Kovacevic et al., 2024). People can only be committed to what they have signed if they were reasonably in a position to read it (that is, they cannot be accused of negligence if the effort required was impossible anyway). This will depend on the length of the text and the time required to read it.

H2: Hypothesis on the benefits of epistemic action. Less expected benefit leads to less responsibility: if people think that reading is pointless, they will not do it. One will also expect other users to do the same.

H3: “We both know that you are counting on me” hypothesis (Bonalumi et al., 2022). Moral judgement will depend on whether the platform's expectation that the user will read the text is recognised by both parties. In other words, a breach of commitment is only condemnable if the platform's expectation regarding the reading of the text is mutually recognised.

The company on the contrary can be judged responsible of “hermeneutical injustice”, a form of epistemic injustice by which occurs “when a gap in collective interpretive resources puts someone at an unfair disadvantage when it comes to making sense of their social experiences” (Fricker, 2007). In other words, the company puts people in a situation where the user could potentially have problems.

² McDonald & Cranor (2008) estimated a potential 40 min a day per American citizen, if they were to read every privacy policy.

Methodology

Participants

A sample size of **340** participants was determined using G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2007). The alpha threshold was set to 0.05, with a statistical power of $1-\beta = .98$ and an effect size of 0.25 (Fig. 2). The chosen effect size corresponds to a **medium effect size** according to the criteria established by Cohen (2009).

Since we planned to run non-parametric tests, we added 15% to our desired sample (Lehmann & D’Abrera, 1998). We anticipated that about 25% of participants would not complete the experiment and answer the control questions correctly. The estimated sample size is therefore **488** participants.

Participants are recruited via crowdpanel.io, an online platform that provides a panel of participants for polls and surveys.

Figure 2 – Results of power analysis for Experiment 2

The participants are randomly assigned to the experimental conditions (Table 2). Each experimental group therefore consists of **122** participants.

Source / Experimental group	Group n°1
Source of Scenario 1	Expert
Source of Scenario 2	Non-Expert

Table 2 – Experimental groups (between-subject design) in Experiment 2

Material

The experimental material consists of a fully online Lime Survey. The questionnaire includes socio-demographic questions, questions related to the evaluation of the test scenarios, and additional questions regarding people's attitudes to AI.

A unique scenario (Box 4) was designed to answer our research question and test our hypotheses, declined in 6 versions. These 9 versions differed in 1) the length of the *Terms and Conditions* (short, medium, long i.e. the **effort variable**); 2) whether the expectation that the user would actually read the text is **explicit or implicit**.

Example of scenario (original version in French)

Rose purchased an online service. She overlooked the Terms & Conditions of the contract the site asked her to sign, which stated that she would pay for a 2-year subscription if she didn't cancel her contract within 30 days. She then asked for her contract to be cancelled the following month, when she realised she had made a mistake. Is she justified in her position?

Box 2 – Example of scenario in Experiment 2

Procedure

The study is conducted entirely online. Participants complete it in the following order:

1. Information leaflet and consent form

The information leaflet describes the framework of the research, the material that is about to be presented to the participants, the duration of the study, information on the use of the data collected, respect for the confidentiality of the participants, and specifies their right to withdraw from the study at any time. A reminder that participation is voluntary, and a contact address is also given to participants. Participants then either accept or refuse to continue based on the information they have been given. If the participant does not wish to continue, the questionnaire ends there.

2. Questions about the test scenarios

Participants then access the study itself. They are presented with a unique scenario describing the situation of a user who decides not to read the Terms & Conditions of a website she is interacting with, and in which 1) **the website's expectation regarding the user's behaviour is either explicit or implicit**; 2) **the length of the Terms & Conditions is either short or long**. Participants are then asked to indicate:

- a. the extent to which they think the website expect the user to read the Terms & Conditions
- b. the extent to which they think the user assumes that the website expects the user to read the Terms & Conditions

These questions are presented in a 5-point-Likert scale, and take less than 5 minutes to complete.

3. Questions about AI and socio-demographic questions

Participants then answer questions about their experience of using artificial intelligence and their knowledge of AI systems. They are asked about their frequency of use of artificial intelligences, the contexts in which they usually use them, and their knowledge of how, e.g., ChatGPT works.

Participants then answer questions about the trust they place in artificial intelligence systems. Other questions concern issues relating to data protection, the perceived usefulness of these systems, potential risks, and ethical issues relating to the use of AI.

This part finally includes demographic questions on gender, age category and educational level, and takes about 5 minutes to answer.

4. Debriefing phase

After the questionnaire has been completed, participants are given information about the aim of the experiment, the hypotheses, and the protocol itself. They are offered the opportunity to leave a comment or ask questions. The e-mail address of the researcher is provided, and participants are told that they can contact her by email if they wish to have access to the results of the research.

The data collection for this experiment has started in September 2024.

For the statistical analyses, mixed-effect models are fitted using *R* statistical software, in order to test for the different factors of interest and random effects.

Next steps : Translating the experiment into a cross-cultural survey

In year 3, we will design a survey modelled after the Moral Machine Survey (Awad et al., 2018). The survey questions will be structured around manipulated scenarios, drawing insights from the KT4D participatory design sessions, and incorporating diverse cultural backgrounds in our data collection.

Interim conclusion: the conditions of a truly empowering system

So far in this module, we have highlighted where and how regulation needs to interfere with the way information is exchanged on the Internet, and the impact of new recommendation tools on people's ability to engage in collective deliberation. We clarified what information or what skills people need to avoid falling into the rabbit hole of manipulative techniques designed to optimise user engagement. And by contrast, which regulations are necessary when the burden on users becomes too heavy. On the one hand, a certain form of content curation is necessary, and sometimes desired by individuals. On the other hand, situations where users end up making choices they would not have made if they had had a real opportunity to step back, must be prevented.

In the first section, we clarified the extent to which people were influenced by the content they were exposed to, through the use of personalised algorithms, which tend to favour psychologically attractive content and make engagement as intense as possible. The second section looked at the problem posed by architectures designed to manipulate individuals on the Internet, by concealing the intentions of online service providers. It addresses the challenge of architectures designed to manipulate (sometimes in good faith) individuals on the internet, emphasising the need for a balance between necessary content curation and the preservation of user autonomy.

Efforts in terms of both education and regulation should aim to better align between the interests of individuals and the objectives they set for themselves on the one hand, and their interactions in a world governed by content derived from AI-based algorithms on the other.

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